

JURISPRUDENCE

THE BALANCE OF THE PRINCIPLES OF COMPETITIVENESS AND INQUISITORIALITY IN THE CONTEXT OF SECURING A CLAIM: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GEORGIAN LEGISLATION

Tornike Merebashvili
Kaspi, Georgia

Abstract

The article reviews the legal mechanism of securing a claim in civil procedural law, which is considered one of the main tools for effective enforcement of court decisions. The focus is on how the mechanism of securing the claim deals with the protection of the rights and interests of the parties, and the right to damages serves the legal rights of the defendants. To protect the interests, so as not to cause unreasonable damage.

The article discusses the importance of the principles of competition and inquisitiveness, which ensure the fairness and impartiality of the legal process. The principle of competition aims at the equality of the parties, while the inquisitorial principle provides for the intervention of the court when the defense party is weak or there are other circumstances that prevent an objective decision from being made.

Keywords: inquisitiveness; competitiveness; compensation for damages; judicial practice; Civil Procedure Law.

Introduction

In civil procedural law, the provision of a claim is one of the important mechanisms designed to ensure the effective enforcement of court decisions. The use is of crucial importance in the context of the protection of the rights and interests of the parties. The right to compensation for damages caused by securing a claim, which is aimed at protecting the legal interests of the defendants, ensures that the process of securing a claim does not go beyond the principle of justice and that the defendant is not unjustly harmed.

In the article, special attention is paid to the analysis of two fundamental principles, competitiveness and inquisitiveness. The principle of competition implies that the parties should have an equal opportunity to defend their positions. At the same time, the inquisitorial role of the court implies the necessity of its intervention, especially in cases where the positions of the defense side are weak or other circumstances may limit the impartiality of the decision. There is a need to strike a balance between these principles to ensure that the parties' legitimate interests and property are protected. The work, which is based on comparative legal, historical-toponymic, and hermeneutic methods, examines how modern Georgian law deals with these challenges and what mechanisms it uses to maintain said balance.

1. Claim, its elements, and factual bases

The right of the court is guaranteed by the Constitution of Georgia¹. For the court to start proceedings, a claim and the consent of the person

presenting the claim are necessary². The subject of the lawsuit has the main significance³. The content of the claim and the claim request must be justified by the claimant⁴. Legislation allows several claims of the plaintiff to be combined in one lawsuit, even if they are related to the same defendant⁵. It should be noted that in claims of attribution, the claim represents a material legal claim of the plaintiff to the defendant, which the court must consider and make its decision against⁶. Taking into account the Civil Procedure Code of Georgia, it is necessary to mention the name of the court, the name of the plaintiff or his representative, the main address of the witness, other persons to be invited to the session, and the main address of the party, in addition, it is important to define the subject of the dispute, the price of the claim, the specific facts and circumstances to be fully established⁷, to establish the plaintiff's request and outline the legal bases employing which the claimant will prove his demands.

The claim has an internal structure - content. The legal nature of any claim should differ not only in its formal sign but also in its content⁸. When characterizing the claim in the civil process, the term "elements of the claim" is used, which implies that the constituent parts of the claim determine its understanding and individuality⁹. Claim elements allow one to distinguish one claim from another, which emphasizes its practicality.

The factual basis of the claim means the means of protection of the legal interest¹⁰, as well as legal facts, the connection of which, from a material legal point of

¹ Article 31 of the Constitution of Georgia.

² Z. Akhvlediani, Z. (2004). The concept of a lawsuit. Tbilisi: Meridian, p. 12.

³ Liluashvili T. (2005). Civil Procedure Law. Tbilisi: p. 197.

⁴ Article 178 of the Civil Code of Georgia.

⁵ Article 182 of the Civil Code of Georgia.

⁶ Liluashvili T. (2005). Procedural law of Georgia. Ex. II . p. 198.

⁷ Article 178 of the Civil Procedure Code of Georgia

⁸ Tskitishvili M. (2021). A lawsuit in a civil process. Tbilisi: Grigol Robakidze University. p. 70.

⁹ Добровольский А.А. (1965). Исковая форма защиты права (основные учения об иске) Moscow.

¹⁰ Die dogmatische Bedeutung des richterlichen Schuldnerschutzes in der Zwangsvollstreckung. Diss. Heidelberg

view, leads to the change or termination of the rights and obligations of the subjects.

There are different opinions of scholars regarding the nature of the claim, in terms of its factual and legal basis. Separation of the legal basis in the lawsuit along with the factual basis follows from the fact that the lawsuit is a demand for the protection of rights and legal interests¹¹. Thus, the court carries out the protection of violated interests¹², when deciding such cases, when the court must make sure, as part of the existence of the right itself, as well as whether the specific right belongs to the person submitting the claim.

The factual basis of the claim refers to legal facts, i.e. documents giving rise to rights. The factual basis of a claim is one of two main parts, and the other part is the legal basis. It should be noted that some scholars disagree with the opinion on legal facts and believe that the claimant should not be refused to file a claim if he does not have a legal justification for the claim in the claim statement¹³. Scientists emphasize the fact that the legal basis of the lawsuit was not based on the law¹⁴. The fact that the plaintiff is not obliged to indicate the norms of the law in the lawsuit is explained by the fact that the legislator tries to make justice as accessible as possible¹⁵. Despite the existence of the legal basis of the claim, it is impossible to interpret it as a legal relationship, since it does not include all types of the claim.

It should be noted that the institution of the lawsuit will help the goal that the party wants to achieve. Access to justice has made the civil process more efficient. Despite the different opinions of scholars in understanding the elements of a claim, each element plays a significant role in the context of protecting the plaintiff's legal interest, and their recognition is necessary for effective justice.

2. Protection of the legal interests of the defendant in case of loss caused by the security measure

By implementing a claim security measure, the defendant's authority to dispose of his property may be limited¹⁶. Indemnification of the damage caused by securing the claim serves the interest of the defendant¹⁷. The said institution is a guarantee that if the claim security measure turns out to be illegal, compensation for the loss caused by the limitation of the defendant's property will be guaranteed¹⁸. However, it should be noted that the burden of proof on the part of the

defendant is the amount of damage caused to him by the security measure. The mentioned order derives from the principle of equality of the parties. Significantly, the legal interests of plaintiffs and defendants are proportionally placed in the orbit of civil procedural law. The legislation of Georgia, in particular the Code of Civil Procedure, provides the right of the defendant to apply to the court for compensation of damages caused by the use of a security measure. At the same time, a person who uses a claim security measure can apply for compensation for damages caused by the claimed security. However, when using the measure, both in the damage and in the part of securing the claim itself, the court can decide on its use within the framework of the Inquisition. Thus, according to civil procedure law, if the plaintiff requires the security of the claim, the defendant can request a guarantee of the insurance of risks expected in the future by securing the claim. This measure creates a certain balance and proportion between the principles of competition between the parties and the inquisitiveness of the court.

The Civil Procedure Code of Georgia provides for the protection of the defendant's interests as well¹⁹. Compensation of damages is carried out by the claimant when the claim was not satisfied by the court and the defendant was harmed by securing the claim or by not submitting the claim within the stipulated time²⁰.

The defendant can proportionally request the provision of countervailing protection, which will equalize the legal positions of him and the plaintiff. This implies the possibility of protecting one's interests within the framework of a "reciprocal security measure"²¹. In one of the cases, the Supreme Court of Georgia explained that "the provided retaliatory security is a means of the legal protection of the interests of the defendant"²², which provides compensation for the damage caused by an unjustified measure. The court is authorized to guarantee the claim both on its initiative and based on the defendant's application. However, in both cases, its use depends on the expected - possible harm. The request to provide a guarantee for the claimant should be based on the applicant's reference to specific circumstances and appropriate justification for the need to provide a guarantee.

The study finds out that in the case of the establishment of non-uniform practice in Georgia, signs of which can be observed, the principle of objectivity of the court may be violated. This is

¹¹Рябова Е.В. (1964). Basis of demand in the Soviet civil process dis... канд. jurid. Nauk. Moscow. 70.

¹²Tskitishvili M. (2021). suit civil in the process Tbilisi: Grigol Robakidze named after University. p. 76.

¹³Tskitishvili M. (2021). suit civil in the process Tbilisi: Grigol Robakidze named after University. pp. 75-76.

¹⁴Викут М.А. (1976). Иск as an element of the right to judicial protection, its legal nature and justification Questions of the theory and practice of the civil process. Saratov. 58-59.

¹⁵Викут М.А. Amendment of the claim in civil litigation as a means of protection of material law. Moscow. 21.

¹⁶К. Enchoshvili N. (2020). of the lawsuit Provision. Tbilisi: TSU. p. 21.

¹⁷ Khrustali V., Liliashvili T. (2007). Georgia civil Procedural of the code Comments. Tbilisi.

¹⁸ Gagua i . (2012). assertion cargo civil Procedural in law. Tbilisi: p. 71.

¹⁹ Georgia Civil Procedural Article 199 of the Code.

²⁰ Zabambashvili Z. (2018). of the lawsuit with provision caused by damage compensation Provision. Warm: Journal of Law of Tbilisi State University.

²¹ Georgia Supreme Court civil affairs of the Chamber of November 25, 2015, ruling on the case N AS -1165 1095 2015.

²² of Georgia Supreme Court Civil Affairs of the Chamber of November 28, 2016, ruling Case # AS -859-825-2016.

expressed by non-uniform decisions in similar cases. In one case, the court uses the initiative of collateral or collateral damages within the framework of inquisitiveness, and in another case, it does not. Therefore, the study recommends that the Civil Procedure Code be amended with the text - *"Based on the established practice in the case of the same claim elements and content, the court is obliged to make a uniform decision, which will concern the security of the claim or the loss caused by the security of the claim."*

3. Collateralized loss

The court process is based on the principle of competition between the parties. In Georgia, as well as in civilized states where the rule of law prevails, the right of the court is constitutionally protected²³. The right to submit a lawsuit is not only a theoretical right written on paper, nor should it be perceived as such, but its practicality should be ensured so that the legally binding decision of the court is enforced²⁴. Accordingly, the person who defends his rights through the court should be protected from the expected obstacles to the guaranteed execution of the²⁵ decision. The court disposes of the property of the parties with the claim request and the measure of securing the claim²⁶. The Civil Procedure Code of Georgia envisages such measures as seizure or any other restrictions on private property²⁷. Regardless of the efficiency of the court, the main indicator of its work is the execution of a fair and legal decision²⁸.

According to the legislation of Georgia, everyone is guaranteed the protection of their rights by judicial procedure. The principle of disposition is defined, as providing for the right of the parties to refuse to proceed with the case and to end the process with the settlement, as well as the principles of competition and equality, which must be respected by the court. The claim security measure is legally regulated in Georgia, which is in line with the European legal system²⁹. The European legal system allows the claimant to protect his legal interests with a security measure until the court makes a final decision³⁰. Security measures in the civil process are mainly aimed at the realization of the defendant's property as a means of guaranteeing the

plaintiff's claim³¹. In the European doctrine, the "claim security measure" is defined as - aimed at maintaining the factual and legal situation³² to protect the rights of both the plaintiff and the defendant. A claim security measure is a means of effective use by the court so that future decision is practically enforced³³.

The Civil Procedure Code of Georgia provides for the measure of compensation for damages caused by securing a claim³⁴. In terms of judicial practice in Georgia, there is a precedent for postponing execution, in the part of securing a claim. This is significant because the relationship between the court and the parties is regulated in this direction, it refers to cases when there is an objective assumption that without postponing the security measure, the issue of the objective result in the case and the enforcement of the court's decision will be significantly complicated³⁵. German law is well aware of the mechanisms of insurance for the expected risks for the execution of the decision by the court because it is possible that if the restriction measure is not postponed, a worse result will occur³⁶.

In Georgia, the interests of both parties are protected to a certain extent when securing a claim. Along with the rights of the plaintiff, the legal interests of the defendant and the balance between them are significant, because the model states: that in the USA and Germany, compensation for damages caused by securing a lawsuit, as well as decisions made independently by the court, are made without the defendant's request³⁷. Accordingly, there is a balance that, on the one hand, the court, within the framework of inquisitiveness, will issue a decision and intervene in the process, on the other hand, based on the principle of competition, the party must condition the realization of the right, so the proportion is significant. In the German Code of Civil Procedure, the content of the claimed security is determined from Article 916 to Article 945 inclusive. Taking into account the German legislation, the party may request both seizure of the property and monetary security³⁸. The imposition of such restrictions becomes necessary when there is a reasonable assumption that the legally binding decision may not be enforced due to the circumstances. Thus,

²³ Georgia Article 31 of the Constitution.

²⁴ Zabambashvili Z. (2018). of the lawsuit with provision caused by damage compensation Provision. Warm: Journal of Law of Tbilisi State University. p. 5.

²⁵ Kramer X. (2003). Harmonization of Provisional and Protective Measures in Europe, Publishes in Storme M. 305-319

²⁶United States Code, Title 28 - JUDICIARY AND JUDICIAL PROCEDURE

²⁷Kipiani N. (2019). Legal and contractual scope of limitation of ownership rights. Tbilisi: TSU.

²⁸Liluashvili T. (2005). Procedural law of Georgia. Ex. II. p. 299.

²⁹Sierra S. (2004). Provisional Court Protection in Administrative Disputes in Europe: The Constitutional Status of Interim Measures Deriving from the Right of Effective Court Protection. A Comparative Approach, European Law Journal, Vol. 10, 42-60.

³⁰Tsikrikas, D. (2008). The European dimension of provisional measures. pp. 700

³¹Rozalinova, E., Angelov. (2012). Jurisdiction, recognition, and enforcement of provisional and protective measures, Revista Forumul Judecatorilor 81. 80-85.

³²Pretelli, I. (2017). Provisional and Protective Measures in the European Civil Procedure of the Brussels I System, Brussels Ibis Regulation, Short Studies in Private International Law.

³³Bariatti, S. (2011). Cases and Materials on EU Private International Law. 940-945.

³⁴Articles 2 and 5 of the Civil Procedure Code of Georgia.

³⁵(2010) Practical recommendations of the Supreme Court of Georgia on issues of civil procedural law for judges of general courts. Chapter II: 157

³⁶Pretelli, I. (2017). Provisional and Protective Measures in the European Civil Procedure of the Brussels I System, Brussels Ibis Regulation, Short Studies in Private International Law.

³⁷Schwartz JC (2016). Civil Procedure ninth edition. 232-237

³⁸German Zivilprozessordnung Art. 916-945

the German judge may resort to inquisitiveness in the case and settle the said issue himself, as well as in the case of compensation for collateral damage.

In the United States of America and other countries with Anglo-American legal systems, the court refuses to secure a claim, unless it is substantiated that the plaintiff has suffered some special loss or the plaintiff has not properly substantiated the motive for securing the claim, because the American model looks at the issue of preliminary preventive in an approach so as not to cause damage to the opposing side³⁹.

In the partner country of Georgia - Ukraine, surprisingly, procedural law in this regard has been regulated in just a few years⁴⁰. More specifically, for "counter-security" in terms of the defendant's interests. His role in civil procedural issues was highlighted and the defendant was given a shared right under procedural law, which equaled the rights of the plaintiff⁴¹. The mentioned right is considered in Ukrainian legislation and scientific sources as a prevention from abuse of the right by the claimant⁴². Also, the norms of the Civil Procedure Code of Ukraine regulate the balance between inquisitiveness and the principle of competition⁴³.

In the United States of America, in particular, in the state of California, the procedural issues of securing a claim and compensation for damages arising from a claim are clearly defined. A balance is maintained between inquisitiveness and the principle of competition. However, it is worth noting that in the United States of America, the judge has the right to apply for the measure of compensation for damages based on the security of the claim without showing the will of the defendant (party)⁴⁴. In the legal scientific literature, it is clear that maintaining such a balance should not be associated with an extreme measure that gives more priority to any of the above-mentioned principles⁴⁵. In Georgia, the court is given the right by the law to direct the process, regardless of the principle of competition. However, as comparative legal research has found out on the example of other countries, there is a need to balance the two conflicting, but in tandem, principles of competition and judicial inquisitiveness. Thus, when considering a specific case, the application of these two principles should be carried out in such a way as not to endanger the establishment of the objective truth. There are cases when the court does not apply the principle of inquisitiveness and does not get involved in the process, which should not be perceived as extreme passivity⁴⁶, because in one of the cases the cassation chamber explained that "despite the

possibility of the court's intervention in the case, the need to use the security guarantee is not confirmed"⁴⁷.

The provision of a claim and the possibility of compensation for damages caused by the provision of a claim guarantee practicality, because only theoretical reasoning and decision-making cannot lead to the occurrence of a legal result. It is necessary to get the result practically⁴⁸. Also, the balance of these two institutions has a great significance⁴⁹.

Conclusion

The legislation and judicial practice of Georgia regulates the securing of a claim and the assessment of damages caused by the securing of a claim, taking into account the interests of both the plaintiff and the defendant. Taking into account the principle of inquisitoriality, the court should act more freely to proportionately balance the rights of the parties and avoid encroachment on the interests of the defendant.

Compensation for damages caused by the security of the claim does not contradict the principle of competition and is used to protect the legal interest of the defendant. This measure is preventive and ensures the justice of the execution of the decision.

The judicial practice of Georgia considers the measure of securing Sakarcheli as a temporary restriction, during which it is important to maintain a balance between the protected good and the limited right. The court must provide damages if the security measure is unjustified or there is a risk of damages.

It is recommended that the text of the article proposed in the article be defined in the Code of Civil Procedure.

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⁴¹The code of civil procedure of Ukraine 1618 IV.

⁴²Khanyk-Pospolitik Roksolana. (2020). Reform of civil procedure law of Ukraine. 9.

⁴³2021. The Institute of Counter-security as a novelty of the reform of the civil procedure law of Ukraine. P.204.

⁴⁴California Code of Civil Procedure 2006 publisher West Group. P.120-150

⁴⁵Rosenberg/Schwab/Gottwald, 2010 Zivilprozessrecht, Neubearbeitete Aufl., München, 395-96.

⁴⁶Zabambashvili Z. (2018). of the lawsuit with provision caused by damage compensation Provision. Warm: Journal of Law of Tbilisi State University. p. 6.

⁴⁷Judgment of the Civil Affairs Chamber of the Supreme Court of Georgia of December 25, 2011, in case N AS-1561-1561-2011.

⁴⁸De Vitte, B. (2009). Human Rights in International Investment Law and Arbitration Edited by PM DUPUY F FRANCIONI and EU PETERSMANN. 25.

⁴⁹Perlmutter RM (2007). Interim Measures and Civil Litigation, 31.

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